

**SURVEY OF INFRASTRUCTURE FOR ART EDUCATION IN SECONDARY
SCHOOLS OF AMRITSAR DISTRICT**

Mrs. Amardeep Kaur

Asst. Prof.

D.A.V. College Of Education For Women, Amritsar

Abstract

This present study deals with the survey of infrastructure for art education in secondary schools of Amritsar district. A Sample was consisted of hundred students from government and private schools and twelve teachers of art from selected schools with purposive random sampling technique. Two self made questionnaires for students and teachers were used to collect the data .The findings of present research revealed that more stress was laid on theoretical and practical sides were ignored. In Majority of schools the art funds were used for other purpose.

Introduction

“Art is the thought of the spirit, so the outer form of the man is alive only when his inner self is living.”

- Mahatma Gandhi

“Art is the expression of feeling which can influence the human mind with intensity”

-French Critic

Education deals with human nature which has its own potential and pace of growth. Art is an expression of feelings and emotions. It is a communication of man’s deepest instincts and ideas reconciled with the social and cultural heritage. In the words of Tagore “Art is response of an individual’s creative soul to the call of the real.”

Art Education is the area of learning that is based upon the visual, tangible Arts Drawing, Painting, Sculpture and Design in Jewelry Pottery, Weaving, and Fabrics etc. Art is the personal feeling of a person and every person is unique .He has his own likings, disliking and views. So every person defines art according to his own interest .Time to time artists and intellectuals have given their views about art. Mostly the word ‘Kala’ has been used for the Fine arts and shilpa (Craft) for the arts of utility Panini used the Word ‘Shilpa’ for both Fine arts and Utility arts. The special activity which is used to make an object beautiful is known as ‘Kala’.

The main purpose of Art Education is to develop creativity, individuality and expression through art activities. Art Education fosters cultural awareness and promotes cultural practices and is the means by which knowledge and appreciation of the arts and culture are transmitted from one generation to the next.

Definitions of Art given by different Artists:

“Man expressed himself through art” - Tagore

“Art is imitation of truth” - Plato

“Art is imitable”- Aristotle

In the field of Education art occupies a significant place in the educational curriculum of a country. Today the educationists have fully realized the importance of art, physical and psychological aspects or in other words in the harmonious development of a learner. Art is essential like air and water for human life without it man would not have gained any culture and civilization near his mind trained and educated properly for the appreciation of beauty in all its manifestations. Art gives pleasure and develop self movement in child .As child grows and makes fields for self expression and self realization it improves the

power of observation and accuracy power of invention proportion harmony and makes honesty in workmanship .Art gives the visible from the ideas feelings and emotional of man which will give satisfaction to a person's mind. Art is everywhere. We are surrounded by art. Art is a mirror through which one can see gradual and constant development of his own personality.

Justification Of The Problem

In the field of Education Art occupies a significant place in the educational curriculum of a country. There is a need to progressively expand facilities of Art Education in school particular at Secondary level. At the present status of Art Education provided in School is not up to the mark that the students feel satisfied with it. Students are compelled to join private hobby classes which are double economic burden on the parents. They are paying in school as well as at private centers. This position involves the researcher take present study for further investigation.

Key Terms Described

Art: The Word 'Art' is derived from the Greek word 'ar' which means to create to make or to fit. "Art is a Creation of beauty which gives pleasure"

Education: Education is an all round development and drawing out of the best in child and man body mind and spirit.

Art Education: Art education is education of Art, which is creative impulse, pure and conscience talented upsurge in mind, nascent ideas, find susceptibilities and instinctive heritage of a man and drawing is the self expressive subtle expanance and on essence of all desires of wind exhibited methodically. It is like giving an ordinary object a new space in a special way.

According to dictionary of education, Art education means, "Instruction and practice in the visual and space arts as carried on in the schools, frequently recognized major areas are fine industrial graphic, advertising on commercial ,domestic or household, civic and theatre arts, minor subdivisions include drawing design, color, construction, history of art and art appreciation.

Infrastructure: The word infrastructure has been used in English since at least 1927, originally meaning "The installations that form the basis for an operation or system."

Infrastructure in relation to school is basic supporting structure needed for the operation of a school or the services and facilities necessary for a school to function.

Objectives

1. To study the facilities, provided for Art education in Government and Private Schools.
2. To study the Qualification and Experience of Teacher Teaching Art.
3. To study Co-curricular activities provided in Government and Private Schools for the promotion of Art Education.
4. To study the Problems faced by the Teachers and Students of Government and Private Schools.

Plan And Procedure

The investigator collected data from schools affiliated with PSEB and CBSE. She visited both Govt. and Private Schools and selected the sample of 100 students from Govt. and Private schools and 12 teachers' of Art from randomly selected schools with purposive random sampling technique.Data collected will be analyzed with the help of percentage in order to verify the various objectives framed from the present study.

$$\text{Percentage (\%)} = \frac{\text{Obtained Score}}{\text{Maximum Score}} \times 100$$

Major Findings

Hypothesis I

There is a no difference in the facilities provided for Art Education in Government and Private Schools stands accepted.

Table 1. shows the responses given by Teachers regarding facilities, provided for Art education in Government and Private Schools.

Table .1

Showing Responses of question related to the facilities provided for Art education by Teachers

S.No	Statement	% of Response by Teachers
1.	Is there Art room in your school?	100%
2.	Do you allow students in Art room for practical work?	42%
3.	Do you have essel in your Art room?	75%
4.	Do you have different types of Artist books in library?	42%
5.	Does your Art room have proper infrastructure?	75%
6.	Have you arranged proper desks for the students in the Art room?	92%
7.	Are there flannel boards in the Art room?	75%
8.	Do you have almirahs/displays board to store the practical work of students?	75%

It can be concluded that besides having Art room in schools with proper desks arrangement only few teachers allow students in art room for practical work. Students perform Art work in their class room only.

Table 2

Showing Responses of questions related to the facilities provided for Art education by students.

S. No	Statements	% of Response by students
1.	Does your Art teacher take your class daily?	50% (yes) 50% (no)
2.	Is their Art room in school having different charts, models etc?	75% (yes) 25% (no)
3.	How much time do you get in Art room for practical work?	58% (1 period in a week) 30% (Twice a week) 36% (Daily)

From the above data it can be concluded that teachers they don't take their art class daily and moreover there is no regular period of art in school as students get one period in a week or twice a week time for art practical and only few schools provide daily provision of art practical in art room.

So, The Hypothesis I that, " There is a no difference in the facilities provided for Art Education in Government and Private Schools stands accepted.

Hypothesis 2

There is no difference in Qualification and Teaching experience of Teachers in Government and Private schools

Teacher occupies a very important position in teaching learning process. Teacher should have mastery over the subject matter. Space was provided in the questionnaire and on the basis of data made available with the help of questionnaire to get information regarding their qualification.

Table 4.6 and 4.7 shows the qualification and experience of teachers.

Table 3
Showing the qualification of teachers

Qualifications	Number of Teachers	% of Teachers
10+2 Diploma in Art & Craft	5	42%
B.A, B.Ed with Art	1	8%
B.A, Diploma in Art & Craft	1	8%
M.A Fine Art, B.Ed	5	42%

42% of Teachers have 10+2 Diploma in Art & Craft ,8% of Teachers teaching art have B.A, B.Ed with Art and 8% of B.A, Diploma in Art & Craft. 42% of Teachers have Master’s Degree. Thus the hypothesis “There is no difference in Qualification and Teaching experience of Teachers in Government and Private schools” stands rejected.

Table 4
Showing Responses of questions regarding teachers qualifications and experience

S. No	Statement	% of Responses by teachers
1.	Do you have teaching experience of more than 5 years?	92%
2.	Have you ever attended any seminars/Workshops on Visual Art?	42%
3.	Are you a member of any association?	100%
4.	Do you have master degree in Art Education?	42%
5.	Do you often held Art exhibition and competition available to students in schools?	92%

Findings Of Results

From the discussion it can be concluded:

- There is Art room in schools with proper desks arrangement but only few Teachers allow students in art room for practical work and the students perform Art work in their class room only.
- Teachers they don’t take their art class daily and moreover there is no regular period of art in school as students get one period in a week or twice a week time for art practical and only few schools provide daily provision of art practical in art room.
- More stress was laid on theoretical and practical sides were ignored.
- There was lack of book on component course in the library.
- Basic Qualification of Government School Teacher’s is 10+2 and Diploma in Art and Craft. Private Schools prefer Master in Education and Bachelor in Education. So Both of Teachers fulfills their required Basic qualification. So can say that majority of teachers are well qualified with rich teaching experience.
- Majority of the students do take part in co-curricular activities like art exhibitions but not to that extent in art competition held in schools. Few students are not at all interested in taking part in art competition and exhibition.
- In Majority of schools the art funds were used for other purpose.

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